

METHODS OF STRENGTH TRAINING OF ATHLETES WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS ENGAGED IN BLIND SPORTS

Yunusov S.A.

Associate Professor of the Department of Adaptive Physical Culture and Sports Uzbek State University of Physical Culture and Sports, CHIRCHIK
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7485356>

Annotation. The article presents a theoretical and methodological justification and experimental verification of methods of speed and strength training of athletes with visual impairment, aimed at improving physical performance using weightlifting exercises.

Keywords: sports training, exercises, speed and strength training

Relevance.

In order to create the necessary conditions in our country for people with disabilities and disabilities to play sports, ensure their worthy participation in the international sports arena and provide state support, as well as in accordance with the decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020 No. UP-5924 "On measures to further improve and popularize physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and dated October 30, 2020 No. UP-6099 "On measures for the widespread introduction of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports": To determine the main directions of the development of the Paralympic movement: the expansion of conditions for sports for people with disabilities and disabilities, as well as a further increase in sports [1,11,21,31,41,51,61,71,81,]

In recent years, among the world's strongest athletes with visual impairments, the density of results has significantly increased and competition has intensified. In this regard, it becomes necessary to research aimed at finding ways to improve the results of athletes, taking into account the systematization of sports training and the development of such techniques that will be effective for people with visual impairments, taking into account the peculiarities of their psychophysical development [2,12,22,32,42,52,62,72,82,].

In the process of physical development of blind sports, speed and strength training occupies a special place. It is known that muscle strength is the primary basis of human physical development and has an extremely important applied value. [10,20,30,40,50,60,70,80,].

Exercises with weights are a simple and very effective means of strengthening the health and comprehensive physical development of our youth. They develop such vital physical qualities as strength, speed, agility and flexibility.

Meanwhile, it is known that training with such stresses allows you to maximize the ability of the neuromuscular apparatus of the student and his volitional qualities [6,16,26,36,46,56,66,76,86,].

The training of qualified athletes with visual impairments is carried out using the experience of training athletes without deviations in health, which does not always lead to the achievement of the planned results. This is due to the peculiarities of disabled athletes and insufficient educational and methodological support for their competitive and training processes [5,15,25,35,45,55,65,75,85,]

In addition, the not always justified sequence of the use of basic training tools, high volumes and insufficient consideration of the peculiarities of the development of the body of young men in this age period do not allow us to qualitatively form a specialized foundation for further improvement of sports skills of athletes with visual impairment [8,18,28,38,48,58,68,78,88,]. At the same time, coaches often build the training process at the stage of in-depth specialization in a similar way to high-class athletes, without taking into account the individual characteristics of athletes with visual impairment, which also does not ensure progressive growth of sports results in the long-term aspect [4,14,24,34,44,54,64,74,84,].

Thus, the relevance of our research is determined by the contradiction that has arisen between the objective need of practice in improving the process of training the sports reserve of athletes with visual impairment, on the one hand, and the insufficient development of scientific and methodological support for this process, on the other. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,77,87].

The purpose of the work is the theoretical and methodological substantiation and experimental verification of methods of speed and strength training of athletes with visual impairment, aimed at improving physical performance using weightlifting exercises.

Tasks:

1. To substantiate the effectiveness of a special auxiliary exercise "jumping out with a barbell" and the traditional method of preparing sports for the blind.
2. To determine the methodology of speed-strength training of athletes with visual impairment using special speed-strength exercises.
3. To identify the impact of the development of speed-strength training in athletes with visual impairment on achieving the best result in strength and speed-strength indicators.

Research methods. To solve the tasks, the following methods were used:

1. Analysis and generalization of literature data.
2. Pedagogical observations.
3. Testing.
4. Instrumental method.
5. Pedagogical experiment.
6. Methods of mathematical statistics.

Organization of research.

The study was conducted in several stages.

At the first stage – from October 4, 2021 to December 18, 2021, the analysis of literary sources on the research problem was carried out, a scientific and methodological apparatus was formed, an experimental methodology was developed. At the second stage, the selection of special exercises was carried out, the development of a training program for the first stage of preparation was carried out, preliminary testing was carried out, forming an experiment that lasted from January 17 to March 28, 2022. The third stage - the final one (April-June 2022) - included analysis and statistical processing of the results obtained.

The results of the survey and their discussion.

For athletes specializing in any kind of sport, a high basic strength potential is a prerequisite, but in no case a guarantee of achieving high athletic results. Even capacious and intensive strength training will not have a positive impact on the development of special qualities if it does not reflect the specific features of the corresponding sports discipline [1].

In the theory and practice of sports, the main means for developing strength and changing the quality of muscles in the desired direction is considered to be training with weights. In modern terms, this is a systematic, well-planned exercise program, in which an athlete uses a barbell, dumbbells and other projectiles and weights, as well as his own weight. As already mentioned, strength training in any sport should correspond to the specifics of specialization [1].

It should be borne in mind that any method of developing strength, if it is repeated for a long time, will not give the desired result. Methods should be changed or supplemented with one another [1].

Special exercises for developing strength should be done in the preparatory period (in the first half of it), so that there is enough time for special technical and tactical training before the competition. This does not mean that strength exercises should not be used in other stages, strength stages should develop in parallel with the improvement of techniques and tactics of fighting and always be an integral part of them, but in different dosages [1].

When selecting the means of special strength training, the following requirements should be followed:

- first of all, it is necessary to load and develop muscle groups and their antagonists directly involved in sports work;
- it is necessary to take into account the competitive movement in space (to choose such special exercises that completely or partially coincide with the movements typical of this sports discipline in structure;
- it is necessary to take into account the efforts spent on overcoming resistance;
- the speed and strength characteristics of the training exercise should coincide with the characteristics of the competitive movement;
- the mode of operation of the neuromuscular system, characteristic of competitive movement, should also be maintained when performing special exercises;
- the duration of the stimuli, i.e. the endurance component must meet the competitive conditions;
- it is necessary to take into account the state of the body, in which special movements are performed in competition conditions;
- it is also necessary to take into account the psychological state of the athlete, which is closely related to the loads carried.

Methodological characteristics should be based on the choice of strictly directed means in the execution mode of 96-100% of the maximum, the magnitude of the load, the use of a sensitive period of development of high-speed qualities [1].

Two methods are used to develop speed qualities: direct and indirect.

Direct methods: repeated, dismembered and sensory.

The indirect method is based on the obligatory preliminary study of the technique of high-speed exercise: the development to optimal mobility of the joints that participate in the high-speed exercise, the development of the strength of the muscle groups involved in the high-speed exercise [1].

In sports practice, they measure: the pace of movements per unit of time, the acceleration time to the maximum, the braking time, the time of a holistic exercise [1].

The physiological basis for the development of strength are the following processes: reduction of as many muscle units as possible, relaxation of antagonist muscles and preliminary stretching of synergist muscles.

FUNCTIONAL GROUPS OF PERSONS UNDERGOING SPORTS TRAINING IN THE FORM OF BLIND SPORTS

Functional groups	Degree of functional limitations	Degree of visual impairment
Group I	Functional capabilities are significantly limited, the athlete needs outside help during training sessions or participation in sports competitions	Complete loss of vision
Group II	Functional capabilities are limited by sufficiently pronounced impairments	Pronounced visual impairments
Group III	Functionality is limited slightly	Mild visual impairment

Exercises for the development and improvement of strength:

1. Static exercises with your own weight. 2. Exercises with stuffed balls. 3. Jumping exercises. 4. Exercises with a partner: squats with a partner on the shoulders, exercises with overcoming the resistance of a partner, etc. 5. Exercises with shock absorbers. 6. Exercises with weights. 7. Exercises on athletic simulators. To a greater extent, exercises for the development of strength should be used in the preparatory period of training and to a lesser extent in the competitive period.

The manifestation of force with maximum acceleration (for example, the force developed when the jumper is repelled). Exercises for the development of special strength: 1. Running for short distances – from 15 to 30 meters. 2. Jumping by pushing one or two legs in different directions. 3. Jumping in a squat forward-backward, left – right. 4. Jumping up with a pop over your head. 5. Cross-step running in different directions. 6. Chest press by beating [1].

conclusions.

1. The wide range of means and weights used, which are most appropriate for the development of strength, reflects the need for such training, in which the strength of the stimulus should increase.

2. Power work requires a lot of energy. Therefore, it is best done in the form of a separate training session. Such a lesson should be preceded by a rest sufficient to restore the energy resources of the body spent on the previous lesson. In addition, after a power load, rest or specific work of moderate volume and optimal intensity is also necessary, contributing to the activation of protein synthesis and the development of working muscle hypertrophy. Specialized power load, as the main condition causing this process, loses all meaning if it is performed as an addition to other work or in a tired state. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,77,87].

3. No means of educating strength training can be considered universal or very effective. Each of them can (and should) be of primary importance at a particular stage of training, depending on the level of fitness of the athlete, the nature of the previous training, specific tasks not of the current stage. Therefore, if we talk about the absolute effect of power training education, then it should be associated, first of all, with a systemic principle that provides for an expedient sequence of introducing various means into the training process, as well as an objectively determined continuity and interrelation of their training effects on the body.

4. It is always necessary to take into account (feel) the strength of the training effect of the means set by the trainer. These funds should carry a developing potential in relation to the current state of the athlete's body. If their potential is below this level, they are useless (this is

an inefficient waste of energy), if higher, they are dangerous (they will lead to overstrain of the body and the motor apparatus). The correct determination of the strength of the training effect is objectively necessary for the athlete.

5. The weight of the barbell from 70 to 130% of the maximum allows you to successfully develop strength qualities. If the weight of the barbell is approximately 85-88%, then with three approaches to the barbell, 6 repetitions are optimal.

6. In the training process, the methods of strength development depend primarily on the volume and intensity of the total load and the ability of athletes to carry these loads.

7. The hypothesis about the expediency of using the shock method of developing explosive muscle strength to increase the level of special speed and strength training of weightlifters-dischargers at the stage of pre-competitive training has been fully confirmed;

8. Deep jumps give a significant increase in the absolute and explosive strength of the muscles after the increase in their value slows down and stabilizes as a result of volumetric loads in exercises with a barbell. The optimal dosage of deep jumps in one training session is 4 series of 10 repulsions;

9. The use of deep jumps at the stage of pre-competitive preparation provides a significant increase in results in the jerk and push of the barbell;

10. Deep jumps also provide a higher increase in the level of speed and strength training of athletes:

11. It is advisable to include deep jumps in training four weeks before the competition and perform during the first three weeks 3 times a week. The optimal volume of deep jumps is 300-360 jumps.

References:

1. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).

2. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)

3. M. X. Mirjamolov, R. F. Odilov, N. Y. Valiyeva, D. B. Baxtiyorov KO'RISH QOBILYATIDA NUQSONI BO'LGAN TALABALARDA HARAKAT KOORDINATSIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH USLUBIYATI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №12. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ko-rish-qobilyatida-nuqsoni-bo-lgan-talabalarda-harakat-koordinatsiyasini-rivojlantirish-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)

4. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).

5. Kh M. M., Svetlichnaya N. K., Abdiev Sh. A., Davlatova LT, Sobirova LB Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan // Psychology and education. – 2021. – Т. 58. – №. 2. – С. 1379-1389
6. Lola Tilapovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-texnologiyalarining-dolzarbligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
7. Л. Б. Собирова КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ БУЗИЛГАН БОЛАЛАРНИ СПОРТ ФАОЛИЯТИ ШАРОИТЛАРИГА МОСЛАШИШ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-obiliyati-buzilgan-bolalarni-sport-faoliyati-sharoitlariga-moslashish-hususiyyatlari> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
8. Шерали Хошимович Ғофуров, Баҳодир Хошимович Ғофуров ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА 5x5 ФУТБОЛ СПОРТ ТУРИНИ ОММАЛАШТИРИШ ОРҚАЛИ КЎРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИДА НУҚСОНИ БОР ШАХСЛАР ҲАРАКАТ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-5x5-futbol-sport-turini-ommalashtirish-or-ali-k-rish-obiliyatida-nu-soni-bor-shahslar-arakat-faolligini-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022)
9. Sherali Xoshimovich G'ofurov, Baxodir Xoshimovich G'ofurov NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nogironlar-aravachasidan-foydalanadigan-umurtqa-pog-onasi-shikastlangan-yoshlarning-adaptiv-jismoniy-tarbiyasi> (дата обращения: 15.11.2022).
10. Юнусов С.А. РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПАРАЛИМПИЙЦЕВ ПАУЭРЛИФТЁРОВ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-i-znachimost-psiologicheskoy-podgotovki-paralimpiytsev-pauerliftyorov-vysoko-y-kvalifikatsii> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
11. Юнусов, С. А. "Физическое воспитание школьников в инклюзивном образовании" SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS." Scientific Journal ISSN (2021): 2181-1601
12. Charos Alisher Qizi Berdiyeva JISMONIY IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN TALABA QIZLARDA EGILUVCHANLIK VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-imkoniyati-cheklangan-talaba-qizlarda-egiluvchanlik-va-uni-rivojlantirish-usuliyati> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
Рухиддин 2, [13.12.2022 11:28]
13. Ч. А. Бердиева ЖИСМОНИЙ ИМКОНИЯТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАР ОРГАНИЗМИНИНГ ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ҲОЛАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ УСУЛИ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zhismoniy-imkoniyati-cheklangan-talabalar-organizmining-funksional-olatini-ba-olash-usuli> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
14. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАРНИ МУСОБАҚА ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №7. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-engil-atletikachilarni-musoba-a-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).

15. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ МЕЪЁРЛАШ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-meyorlash> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022)
16. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova ADAPTIV SPORT O'YINLARINI (VOLEYBOL) O'QITISH METODIKASIDA HARAKAT USLUBLARI VA QOIDALARI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptiv-sport-o-yinlarini-voleybol-o-qitish-metodikasida-harakat-uslublari-va-qoidalari> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022).
17. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 12.12.2022)
18. Бобомуродов, Н. Ш. "Структуры физической подготовленности курашистов" Вестник науки и образования научно-методической журнал № 4 (82)." Часть 2.2020 (2020): 41-44
19. Бобомуродов, Н. Ш. "Features of development of physical qualities in the process of sports training of students." International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation 24.09 (2020): 4225-4229.
20. Светличная Н. Коррекционно-педагогическое воздействие на сенсомоторное развитие детей с нарушениями интеллектуального развития // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 379-386.
21. Светличная Н.К. Развитие инклюзивного образования в области адаптивного физического воспитания детей // Вестник Тамбовского университета. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. – 2022. – Т. 27. – № 3. – С. 705-713. – DOI 10.20310/1810-0201-2022-27-3-705-713. ISSN: 1810-0201 (Print). ISSN: 2782-5825 (Online).
22. «Олимпийский спорт и спорт для всех. – 2021. – С. 412-414.
- Валиева Н. Ю., Одилов Р. Ф. МЕТОДЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭФФЕКТА ТОНУСНЫХ РЕФЛЕКСОВ ПРИ ДЕТСКОМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОМ ПАРАЛИЧЕ С ПОМОЩЬЮ ФИТБОЛЬНОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 966-972.
23. Odilov R.F., Valiyeva N.Y.Q. Sensor tizimida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar mashg'ulotlarini kompleks nazorat qilish // Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 670-674.
24. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Зокиров Д. Р. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ ЗДОРОВЬЯ // Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2020. – С. 20-23.
25. Миржамолов М. Х. ЭШИТИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ РИВОЖЛАНМАГАН ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАРБИЯ МАШҒУЛОТЛАРИНИ ЎТКАЗИШ УСЛУБИЯТИ // Scientific progress. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 214-221.
26. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/malakali-sprinterchilarning-sport-mashg-ulotlarini-rivojlantirishning-usullari> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
27. Еофуров Ш. Jismoniy tarbiya vositalari orqali sportchilarni o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish. – 2020.

28. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 13.12.2022).
29. Л. Т. Давлатова БОЛАЛАР ЦЕРЕБРАЛ ФАЛАЖИДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИКНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ВА ИЛМИЙ НАЗАРИЙ СОҲАДА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01.2022).
30. Л. Б. Собирова Эффективность использования специальных упражнений в профилактике нарушений роста у младших школьников // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №5.
31. Sherali Hoshimovich G. Ofurov Qisqa masofaga yuguruvchi sportchilarni mashg'ulotlarini rivojlantirishning usullari //Scientific progress. – 2021. – №. 8.
32. ЖИСМОНИЙ Л., НАЗАРИЙ Т., РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ С. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. № Special Issue 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 12.01.2022).
33. BOLALAR V. A. O'smirlar SPOR MAKTABLARIDA SPORCHILAR TAYYORLANISHINI TAKILISH BOSHLANGAN MASHG'ULOT GURUHI GofurovSh //X. Fan-Sportga. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 38-40.
34. Еофуров Ш. NOGIRONLAR ARAVACHASIDAN FOYDALANADIGAN UMURTQA POG'ONASI SHIKASTLANGAN YOSHLARNING ADAPTIV JISMONIY TARBIYASI //МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКАЯ ОНЛАЙН КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ. – 2021. – Т. 4. – С. 24.
35. ЕОФУРОВ Ш. МАКТАБЛАРИДА БОШЛАНЕИЧ ТАЙЁРЛОВ ГУРУ^ ИДА ШУЕУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАР МАШЕУЛОТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ. – 2020.
36. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. MALAKALI SPRINTERCHILARNING SPORT MASHG'ULOTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USULLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – №. 4.
37. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНИАТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
38. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova ADAPTIV SPORT O'YINLARINI (VOLEYBOL) O'QITISH METODIKASIDA HARAKAT USLUBLARI VA QOIDALARI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/adaptiv-sport-o-yinlarini-voleybol-o-qitish-metodikasida-harakat-uslublari-va-qoidalari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
39. Lola Tilopovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8.

- URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-technologiyalarining-dolzrabligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
40. Л. Т. Давлатова БОЛАЛАР ЦЕРЕБРАЛ ФАЛАЖИДА ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИКНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ВА ИЛМИЙ НАЗАРИЙ СОҲАДА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №Special Issue 1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-tserebral-falazhida-zhismoniy-tayyorgarlikni-mash-ulot-zharayonida-va-ilmiiy-nazariy-so-ada-rivozhlantirish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
41. Юнусов С. А. Особенности периодизации тренировочного процесса атлетов высококвалифицированных парапауэрлифтёров. – 2021.
42. Юнусов С.А. РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПАРАЛИМПИЙЦЕВ ПАУЭРЛИФТЁРОВ ВЫСОКОЙ КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-i-znachimost-psihologicheskoy-podgotovki-paralimpiytsev-pauerliftyorov-vysokooy-kvalifikatsii> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
43. Мирзимова Ф., Давлатова Л. Т. Использование адаптивной физической культуры при обучении студентов с инвалидностью и особыми физическими потребностями // Проблемы і перспективи розвитку спортивних ігор і єдиноборств у вищих навчальних закладах. – 2022. – Т. 1. – С. 138-141.
45. Lola Tilapovna Davlatova JISMONIY TARBIYA VA SPORTDA SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TECHNOLOGIYALARINING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/jismoniy-tarbiya-va-sportda-sog-lomlashtirish-technologiyalarining-dolzrabligi-va-ahamiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
46. Л. Б.Собирова ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ НАРУШЕНИЙ РОСТА У МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/effektivnost-ispolzovaniya-spetsialnyh-uprazhneniy-v-profilaktike-narusheniy-rosta-u-mladshih-shkolnikov> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
47. Kh M. M., Svetlichnaya N. K. Abdiev Sh. A., Davlatova LT, Sobirova LB Improving Pedagogical Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Preparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan //Psychology and education. – 2021. – Т. 58. – №. 2. – С. 1379-1389.
48. Nurullayevna B. S., Sobirova L. МАКТАБГАЧА YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA YASSI OYOQLIKNI JISMONIY MASHG'ULOTLARDA GIMNASTIKA VOSITALARI ORQALI OLDINI OLISH //ТА'ЛИМ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ ТАHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 65-69.
49. Лайло Бахромовна Собирова ГОЛБОЛ-КҶРИШ ҚОБИЛИЯТИ БУЗИЛГАН БОЛАЛАРНИНГ КОРДИНАЦИОН ҚОБИЛИЯТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВОСИТАЛАРИ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/golbol-k-rish-obiliyati-buzilgan-bolalarning-kordinatsion-obiliyatini-rivozhlantirish-vositalari-samaradorligi> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
50. Sobirova L. B. Efficiency of Using Special Exercises for Preventing Scoliosis Initial Age Children //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2018. – №. 6.
51. Sobirova L. B. THE USE PHYSICAL EDUCATION ARRANGEMENT TO PREVENT DISORDERS IN 7-10 GRADE PUPILS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 411-415.

52. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O. et al. Scientific progress. 2022. № 1 //URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 04.02.2022).
53. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
54. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
55. Sherali Hoshimovich G'Ofurov, Dilshod Baxtiyor O'G'Li Baxtiyorov, Umid Abdugaforovich Saidov MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNI YENGIL ATLETIKA MASHQLARI ORQALI MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/maktabgacha-yoshdagi-bolalarni-yengil-atletika-mashqlari-orqali-mashg-ulotlarini-tashkil-etish> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
56. Sherali Hoshimovich G. O., Dilshod Baxtiyor O. G., Li Baxtiyorov U. A. S. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni yengil atletika mashqlari orqali mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
57. Dilshod Baxtiyorovich Baxtiyorov AMPUNTANT FUTBOLCHILARNI JISMONIY TARBIYA VOSITALARI VA USLUBIYATI // Scientific progress. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ampuntant-futbolchilarni-jismoniy-tarbiya-vositalari-va-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
58. Абдурахимова Ш. А., Бахтиеров Д. Б. МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ СИЛОВЫХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ У ЮНЫХ СТРЕЛКОВ 13-14 ЛЕТ И ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СПОРТИВНОГО МАСТЕРСТВА //Рекомендовано к изданию Советом по качеству УралГУФК Протокол № 8 от 14 мая 2018 г. – 2018. – С. 19.
59. Абдиев Ш.А. ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНОЙ НАГРУЗКИ ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ЛЕГКОАТЛЕТОВ С ПОРАЖЕНИЕМ ОПОРНО-ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОГО АППАРАТА // Современное образование (Узбекистан). 2021. №1 (98). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/planirovanie-trenirovochnoy-nagruzki-vysokokvalifitsirovannyh-legkoatletov-s-porazhenim-oporno-dvigatel'nogo-apparata-1> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
60. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ ЕНГИЛ АТЛЕТИКАЧИЛАРНИ МУСОБАҚА ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ // Fan-Sportga. 2020. №7. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-engil-atletikachilarni-musoba-a-yuklamalarini-rezhalashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
61. Абдиев Ш.А. ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ МЕЪЁРЛАШ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-meyorlash> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).

62. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИДА НУҚСОНИ БЎЛГАН ЮҚОРИ МАЛАКАЛИ УЛОҚТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЮКЛАМАЛАРИНИ ОПТИМАЛЛАШТИРИШ // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparatida-nu-soni-b-lgan-yu-ori-malakali-ulo-tiruvchilarni-mash-ulot-yuklamalarini-optimallashtirish> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
63. Шерзод Абдурахмонович Абдиев ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ ТРЕНИРОВОЧНОЙ НАГРУЗКИ ВЫСОКОКВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ЛЕГКОАТЛЕТОВ С ПОРАЖЕНИЕМ ОПОРНО-ДВИГАТЕЛЬНОГО АППАРАТА // Academic research in educational sciences. 2020. №3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/planirovanie-trenirovochnoy-nagruzki-vysokokvalifitsirovannyh-legkoatletov-s-porazhenim-oporno-dvigatel'nogo-apparata> (дата обращения: 11.11.2022).
64. Абдиев Ш.А. Енгил атлетикани ўқитиш методикаси (Адаптив жисмоний тарбия ва спорт) // Ўқув қўлланма- Чирчиқ, Т.; 2020. - 200 б.
65. Миржамолов.М.Х., Абдиев Ш.А. Improving Pedagogikal Mechanisms to Increase Special Physical Pereparation of Students with Disabilities in Uzbekistan.(2021) 58 (2) ISSN:00333077. 317 - 323 Pg.
66. М. Х. Миржамолов, Ч. А. Бердиева ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАРДА СКИБИНСК ИНДЕКСИ БЎЙИЧА ЎРТА АРИФМЕТИК ҚИЙМАТЛАР // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-talabalarda-skibinsk-indeksi-b-yicha-rta-arifmetik-iyamatlar> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
67. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Валиева Н. Ю. ДБ Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ //Scientific progress. – 2022. – №. 1.
68. Миржамолов М.Х. РИО-ДЕ ЖАНЕЙРО ШАҲРИДА БЎЛИБ ЎТГАН XV ВА ТОКИОДА БЎЛИБ ЎТГАН XVI ПАРАЛИМПИА УЙИНЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rio-de-zhaneyro-sha-rida-b-lib-tgan-xv-va-tokioda-b-lib-tgan-xvi-paralimpiya-yinlari-ta-lili> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
69. Миржамолов М. Х. Жисмоний имконияти чекланга укувчи-ларнинг спорт маршрулотларига мослашиши //У^ ув услубий мажмуа, Тошкент. – 2014.
70. М. Х. Миржамолов, Р. Ф. Одилов, Н. Ю. Валиева, Д. Б. Бахтиёров МЕТОДИКА РАЗВИТИЯ КООРДИНАЦИИ ДВИЖЕНИЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ // Scientific progress. 2022. №1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/metodika-razvitiya-koordinatsii-dvizheniy-u-studentov-s-narusheniyami-zreniya> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
71. Salomov R. S., Mirjamolov M. X. Adaptation of students with disabilities to sports is a teaching aid. – 2015.
72. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНИАТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).
73. Миржамолов М.Х. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ // Fan-Sportga. 2022. №2. URL:

<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/para-sportchilarning-kinematik-arakat-imkoniyatlari-talili> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

74. М. Х. Миржамолов, Ч. А. Бердиева ТАЯНЧ-ҲАРАКАТ АППАРАТИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ТАЛАБАЛАРДА СКИБИНСК ИНДЕКСИ БЎЙИЧА ЎРТА АРИФМЕТИК ҚИЙМАТЛАР // Scientific progress. 2022. №4. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-apparati-shikastlangan-talabalarda-skibinsk-indeksi-b-yicha-rta-arifmetik-iymatlar> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

75. Миржамолов М.Х. ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ПАРАЛИМПИА ҲАРАКАТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА ЗАХИРА СПОРТЧИЛАРНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ИЛМИЙ ЁНДАШУВ // Fan-Sportga. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zbekistonda-paralimpiya-arakatini-rivozhlantirish-va-zahira-sportchilarni-tayyorlashda-ilmiy-yondashuv> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

76. М. Х. Миржамолов ТАЯНЧ – ҲАРАКАТ АЪЗОЛАРИ ШИКАСТЛАНГАН ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА МУСКУЛ ФАОЛИЯТИНИНГ БУЗИЛИШ ТАРТИБИ УЧУН ФУНКЦИОНАЛ ТИЗИМ ДИНАМИКАСИ // Scientific progress. 2021. №8. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tayanch-arakat-azolari-shikastlangan-uvchilarda-muskul-faoliyatining-buzilish-tartibi-uchun-funksional-tizim-dinamikasi> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

77. ПАРА-СПОРТЧИЛАРНИНГ КИНЕМАТИК ҲАРАКАТ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ Миржамолов М.Х. Фан-Спортга. 2022. № 2. С. 8-10.

78. Миржамолов М. Х. ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ, УЧАЩИХСЯ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ФИЗИЧЕСКИМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ //Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2019. – С. 50-55.

79. Миржамолов М. Х. Болалар мия фалажида тонус рефлексларининг таъсирини фитбол1 гимнастикаси ёрдамида ривожлантириш услубияти // Современное образование (Узбекистан). 2017. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/bolalar-miya-falazhida-tonus-reflekslarining-tasirini-fitbol1-gimnastikasi-yordamida-rivozhlantirish-uslubiyati> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

80. Mirjamolov M. H. Evaluating Results of Functional Opportunities and Organism Systems Relationship of Students with Limited Physical Opportunity //www. auris-verlag. de. – 2017. – Т. 4. – С. 5.

81. Nayriddinovich M. M. THE RESULT OF THE MARKS OF MUTUAL DEPENDENCE BODY SYSTEM OF THE STUDENT'S WHOSE PHISICAL POSSIBILITY ARE LIMITED AND FUNCTIONAL CAPACITY //ББК 75.03 А 38. – С. 142.

82. Мехриддин Хайриддинович Миржамолов КЎРИШ ИМКОНИАТИ ЧЕКЛАНГАН ШАХСЛАРДА СПОРТ ТЕХНИКАСИГА ЎРГАТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ // Scientific progress. 2022. №6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-rish-imkoniyati-cheklangan-shahslarda-sport-tehnikasiga-rgatishning-ziga-hos-zhi-atlari> (дата обращения: 16.12.2022).

83. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Физическая реабилитация борцов с нарушениями в позвоночнике у квалифицированных борцов //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 874-879.

84. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Technique of Recording Technical and Tactical Actions in Fight Turon //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2018. – №. 4. – С. 16-19.

85. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Юкори малакали курашчиларнинг техник-тактик харакатларини ривожлантириш методикаси // Педагогик таълим" Илмий-назарий журнал. Тошкент. – 2011.
86. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Контроль и анализ действий в борьбе турон // "Фан-спортга" илмий-назарий журналы. Тошкент. – 2011.
87. Бобомуродов Н. Ш. Физиологический подход в прогнозировании перспективности борцов-туронистов // "МуРаллим х, ем узликсиз билимлендириу" илмий-методикалык журнал. Нукус.-2019. – 2019.
88. Миржамолов М. Х., Одилов Р. Ф., Зокиров Д. Р. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ СТУДЕНТОВ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ ЗДОРОВЬЯ // Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта. – 2020. – С. 20-23.
89. Светличная Н.К. Адаптивное и оздоровительное физическое воспитание: учебное пособие. – Toshkent: O'ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI, 2022. – 200 с. ISBN: 978-9943-7751-1-4.
90. Светличная Н.К. Спорт в период пандемии COVID-19 // Фан-Спортга. – 2022. – № 1. – С. 3-7. ISSN: 2181-7804.
URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sport-v-period-pandemii-covid-19>
91. Светличная Н.К. Развитие инклюзивного образования в области адаптивного физического воспитания детей // Вестник Тамбовского университета. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. – 2022. – Т. 27. – № 3. – С. 705-713. – DOI 10.20310/1810-0201-2022-27-3-705-713. ISSN: 1810-0201 (Print). ISSN: 2782-5825 (Online).
URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/razvitie-inklyuzivnogo-obrazovaniya-v-oblasti-adaptivnogo-fizicheskogo-vozpitaniya-detey>
92. Светличная Н. Коррекционно-педагогическое воздействие на сенсомоторное развитие детей с нарушениями интеллектуального развития // Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – № 1. – С. 379-386. ISSN: 2181-1385.
URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/korreksionno-pedagogicheskoe-vozdeystvie-na-sensomotornoe-razvitie-detey-s-narusheniyami-intellektualnogo-razvitiya>
93. Светличная Н.К. Комплексный подход в оценке функционального состояния лиц, занимающихся физической культурой и спортом // Вестник Ташкентской медицинской академии, 2022. Специальный выпуск. – С.385-388. ISSN: 2181-7812.
94. Светличная Н.К. Odamning jismoniy va funktsional tayyorgarligi darajisini baholash usuli. Способ оценки уровня физической и функциональной подготовленности человека: Ixtiro patenti № IAP 07017 // Rasmiy axborotnoma, №8(256), 2022. – С.48-49.
URL: https://my.ima.uz/cert-v1/default/check-patent?check_id=9824c26e1b6bd0951e0392ad4108657a
95. Светличная Н.К. Интеграция в спортивном образовании Узбекистана // Актуальные проблемы адаптивной физической культуры: материалы Всероссийской научно-практической конференции с международным участием. – Омск: СибГУФКС, 2022. – С. 198-204. ISBN: 978-5-91930-207-0.
96. Светличная Н.К. Научно-методическое обеспечение подготовки спортсменов высокой квалификации в Олимпийском и Паралимпийском спорте // Сборник

Международной научно-практической конференции «Современная наука в Олимпийском спорте». – Ташкент: НОК Уз, 2022. – С. 348-352. ISBN: 978-9943-5718-1-5.
97.Светличная Н.К. Спорт и двигательная активность в период пандемии // Сборник Международной научной конференции «Итоги XXXII летних Олимпийских, XVI Паралимпийских Игр 2021 года и вопросы подготовки к очередным Олимпийским и Паралимпийским играм». – Чирчик: УзГУФКС, 2022. – С.140-142.

